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Optimism And Self-Esteem As Correlates Of Academic Achievement Of Secondary School Students In Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the optimism and self-esteem as correlates of academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State. The study was guided by seven research questions and their corresponding null hypotheses. The design for the study is correlational research design. The population for the study consisted of all the 42,624 senior secondary II (SS2) students in the 278 public secondary schools in Rivers State. A sample of 623 students was used for the study. Multi-stage sampling procedure was adopted in drawing the sample. Three instruments were used for the study namely the Optimism Scale (OS), Self-Efficacy Scale (SES) and English Language, Mathematics and Biology Achievement Test (ELMBAT). The Research instruments were validated by the two experts in the field of Measurement and Evaluation. To ensure the reliability of the instruments, Cronbach alpha (α) technique was used for all the instruments. The alpha coefficients of 0.75, 0.82 and 0.87 for optimism, self-efficacy and ELMBAT respectively. The data generated were analyzed using simple and multiple regression analysis. Specifically, research question one and two were answered using simple linear regression while research question three was answered using multiple regression. Regarding the hypotheses, hypotheses one and two were tested using t-test associated with simple linear regression while hypotheses three was tested using ANOVA associated with multiple linear regression. Result revealed among others that optimism and self-efficacy significantly independently and jointly relate with academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State. It was recommended that school counsellors should play an important role in the academic achievement of students by offering and/or referring them for appropriate techniques that will help boost their optimistic behaviour.

Keywords: Optimism, self-esteem, academic achievement, students

INTRODUCTION

Education is the best legacy a nation can give to her citizens especially the youths. This is because education is very important in the development of any nation or community. Education is the process of transmitting what is worthwhile to members of the society. According to Okafor (2018) education embraces all those experiences of the individual through which knowledge is acquired and intellect enlightened. For Nwabachili and Egbue (2019) education is what goes on from one generation to another generation. In this context, education is the process of socializing the child to grow up as a fulfilled

member of the society through informal, formal and non-formal process. Informal education is the process of acquiring knowledge about the environment and beyond through living with one another. According to Nwabachili and Egbue (2019) formal education is a consciously planned form of socialization in a formal setting such as school. They stressed that non-formal education involve all those systematic programmes and processes of education and training that is done outside formal education setting.

The student, who is one of the basic elements of the education system, has from past to present been regarded as the future of society, and in this sense, has been included in a continuous development process. Nations follow the global development process and attempt to foster knowledge, skills, behaviour, competence and ideas in line with this development. For this purpose, education systems aim for students to integrate with the world and speak the same language, attain success, acquire a profession, contribute to the nation, gain the habit of lifelong learning and most important of all, acquire 21st century skills. For countries to be able to realize these aims, it is expected that the factors of the family, the school's physical conditions, the school administration, the school environment and the teacher , which are among the characteristics of efficient schools (Sisman & Turan, 2015), will be continually updated and changed. As well as the realization of these changes, it is essential that academic achievement, which is one of the basic aims of education institutions, should be enabled. It is a fact that the student's academic achievement, which is one of the most basic and indispensable aims of education institutions, is also an expectation of society.

Therefore, when education systems are setting their goals and objectives, they take academic achievement into consideration alongside a number of competences. Achievement is progress made towards attaining one's goals (Wolman, 2013). In other words, achievement can be expressed as progress made towards attaining the goals determined by individuals or institutions. In terms of the student, achievement means reaching the objectives framed in the curriculum (Kazazoglu, 2013). In education institutions, however, the aim of this achievement is to improve and advance academically. Academic achievement is the knowledge, skills, success and development instilled in students by the teacher in schools (Carter & Good, 1973). Academic achievement involves the student's changes in behaviour in all curriculum domains other than behaviours in the psychomotor and affective domains (Ahmann & Glock, 2015). In order to enable academic achievement, it is expected that students will successfully carry out the tasks given to them, display a perfectionist approach, show resistance in the face of obstacles and develop strategies for overcoming difficulties that they face (Cox, 2019).

According to Pruet (2010) academic achievement is the level of achievement attained via the combination of inputs from student's motivation and conduct. Also, academic achievement index (2010) revealed that academic achievement is how students deal with their studies and responsibilities given to them by their teachers.

Louis (2012) posits that academic achievement is the ability of students to obtain high grades and standard test scores in school courses, especially courses that are part of the core academic curriculum. From the foregoing, academic achievement as a major focus of research in the 21st century strengthens the basis for success and excellence in man's drive towards academic growth and development. All through the centuries of human growth, development and civilization one question has remained pertinent in the minds of the older generation: that is how to get the younger generation properly adjusted and capable of not only surviving but thriving in the face of an ever changing, dynamic and unpredictable future. It is for this singular reason that societies all around the world have established some form of education with which to produce citizenry capable of protecting, promoting, and cultivating the ideals of the society. From the classical time, nation-states such as, Rome and Athens formulated goals believed to achieve the above lofty objectives of their respective societies. Historically too, the church was involved in the establishment of educational goals, as it was during the middle ages. It invested heavily in the construction of monasteries, and the training of priests and monks (Muller, 2011).

Students' academic achievement is regarded as the scholastic standing of students at the end of a given study period that is expressed in terms of grades. Student's success in progression and retention are the

major indicators of performance and attainment gaps, students with low performance can easily be identified and effective measures can be put in place to provide interventions to bridge the attainment gap. The attainment gap in this context is the qualitative differences between their performances in the class.

One of the most commonly cited factor responsible for students' academic achievement is optimism. Optimism is hopefulness and confidence about the future or the success of something. According to Pihasniwati et al. (2014) this was the prevailing view of the immediate past century as most scholars and laymen alike believed that an individual's optimistic behaviour is the major predisposing factor for his/her academic achievement.

However, Aremu and Oluwole (2001) and Aremu (2000) have revealed that some other factors also influence or contribute to students' academic achievement. Some of these factors identified include student-teacher relationship, personality, study habit, school readiness, family background, demographic characteristics, motivation, teachers' competence, instructional materials, learning style of students, optimism, self-efficacy and locus of control. These factors, interact with students before, during and after school hours. This therefore highlights the importance of not only understanding them, but promoting them in ways that can positively enhance the skills and competences of students, as well as the development of the Nigerian society. Five of the above factors: critical thinking skill and learning styles are the primary focus of this study.

An attitude of optimism among students will be very helpful in the learning process. Optimistic students will consider failure a challenge that must be faced, and this failure is only temporary. Failure occurs due to factors outside of himself, thus spurring him to overcome and improve until the factors causing the failure disappear from him (Pihasniwati et al., 2014). When he gets a bad grade, an optimistic student thinks that the incident is only temporary, and he is motivated to be even more active in studying to get a better grade. Therefore, optimism needs to be owned and accustomed to by every student because it will affect the learning process and achievement at school. Students who achieve less well are probably caused by students who have the ability but lack optimism. They are not confident in their ability to complete various demands at school, and anxiety arises because they feel burdened by the various demands they have to face (Zukdi et al., 2022). Optimism makes people think positively and realistically when looking at a problem. People who think positively always try to achieve their best. Someone who wants good academic achievement must have a positive mind, a positive attitude, and positive behaviour. Because good achievement is an accumulation of good knowledge, attitudes, and skills. A measure of student performance is learning attainment, which is a change in behaviour that has cognitive, emotional, and psychomotor components. Optimism shows a positive direction and purpose in life. Optimistic students will be more goal-oriented, for example, getting good grades or winning the class. Then, to achieve these goals, students become more enthusiastic about trying, are able to go through various challenges, are able to rise from failures, and have positive beliefs and hopes to be able to realize these goals. This is what causes students to achieve better and more satisfying learning achievements.

Optimism plays an important role in one's success in work, health, social relations, and education. This is in accordance with what was said by previous researchers that optimism is one of the factors in positive psychology that is proven to affect one's existence (Witarsa & Ruhyana, 2021). Optimism is closely related to the positive results one wants, such as the ability to overcome problems, a good moral condition, a good health condition, and good achievement (Prayitno et al., 2017). Pessimistic people have achievements below their potential. Conversely, people who are optimistic are able to excel beyond their potential. Students with high optimism can certainly achieve all their desires, while students who are pessimistic will definitely be hampered in achieving their goals (Dianto et al., 2023). This is because optimistic students have different ways of dealing with pessimistic students. They think that failure is a challenge that must be faced and that failure is only temporary. They are not easy to blame; according to them, failures are caused by other things outside of themselves (Antoni & Mustafa, 2023). This mindset can foster motivation to correct failures by taking actions deemed necessary to achieve what is expected. Thus, it can be said that optimism has an important effect on motivating oneself so that the desired achievements can be achieved (Riyanti et al., 2023). Optimism is a positive attitude that can spur students'

motivation to learn and achieve. Optimistic students are more successful than those who are pessimistic, so they achieve more and avoid depression. However, optimism alone is not enough to achieve good performance but is one of the factors that can help students achieve quality performance (Rosyid, 2019).

Self-efficacy is the belief in one's ability to succeed in a particular situation. Bandura (2012) defines self-efficacy as a belief in a person's ability to succeed in a particular situation or to accomplish a particular task. Beliefs in personal efficacy form an important element of human agency (Bandura, 2012). Bandura said that if people believe they are incapable of producing results, they will not try to make things happen. Academic self-efficacy is mainly about the student's perception of what they can or cannot do as opposed to individual resources. Students with high self-efficacy tend to choose challenging tasks, while students who cannot do well on their own often avoid them. Self-efficacy involves learning to control oneself, which helps the student to use his / her resources to plan, control and analyse the performance of tasks, activities and the preparation of learning products. (Schunk & Zimmerman, 2019). Students with high self-efficacy tend to earn better grades and show greater perseverance in engineering and science subjects than other students with low self-efficacy. In addition, high self-efficacy students use practical comprehension techniques when learning, scheduling their time and managing their efforts.

Due to the fact that the self-efficacy cannot be presumed as the direct reason for the academic achievement, however, it will be the self-regulation that causes the academic achievements. The self-efficacy will cause the use of self-regulation and therefore the relation between self-efficacy and the self-regulation may be defined as follows: self-efficacy for self-regulated learning. The self-efficacy for self-regulated learning refers to the individual's beliefs on application of the self-regulation processes such as the goal setting, self-monitoring, strategy use, self-evaluation and self-reaction (Bandura, 2006). Several researches have shown the positive relation between the self-efficacy and self-regulated learning and the academic achievements (Zimmerman, 2019; Denissen, et al., 2017). The self-efficacy beliefs are important as through them the learning processes, motivations, passion and selectiveness regulates the individual's use in different areas. According to the definition of the self-efficacy for the self-regulation (Bandura 2006) considers the self-efficacy as a born capability that should be organized in behaviour, sensational, social and learning sub-skills including the self-believe (Self-confidence, problem-solving, positive thinks), self-control, regulating the thinks and behaviour to reach the goal, self-evaluation, self-monitoring, positive thinking, controlling the behaviour to reach the goal step by step, and self-simulation to overcome the losing.

Several challenges are encountered by university students including the issues of rising costs, information overload, the continuous need to acquire and develop new skills, and the limited timeframes for achieving the intended learning outcomes. The academic performance of university students in recent days have been worrisome and it seems to be worst among students in Rivers state. Many research aimed at tackling underperforming students have failed to acknowledge the full extent of the causes of poor academic achievement and this call for further investigation. Comments from educators have demonstrated and shown various causes and solutions to poor academic achievement but yet the situation is still on the increase especially in Rivers State. The situation becomes a threat to the future of education not only in Rivers state but the society at large.

It could be observed by the researcher that most of these students become frustrated and fed up with school. This ugly situation has not only pushed most of these frustrated students to resort to examination malpractice but also to abandoning their studies and end up either in unprepared marriages, prostitution and unwanted pregnancies for the females and for the males.

It is strongly believed that a student who does not perform well academically may not want to further his/her education rather may join cult groups and commit nuisance. One begins to wonder what could be responsible for this academic deviation by the students who are supposed to know the relevance of their education as they prepare for life in the Higher Institution. It is on these backdrops the researcher investigated psychosocial correlates of academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The main aim of this study was to investigate psychosocial correlates of academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State. The objectives of this study were specifically: to;

1. Determine the relationship between optimism and academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State.
2. Ascertain the relationship between self-efficacy and academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State.
3. Determine whether optimism and self-efficacy jointly relate with academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions are formulated guided this study:

1. What is the relationship between optimism and academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State?
2. What is the relationship between self-efficacy and academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State?
3. To what extent do optimism and self-efficacy jointly relate with academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant relationship between optimism and academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant relationship between self-efficacy and academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State.
3. Optimism and self-efficacy do not significantly jointly relate with academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The design for the study was correlational research design. The population for the study consisted of all the 42,624 senior secondary II (SS2) students in the 278 public secondary schools in Rivers State. A sample of 623 students was used for the study. Multi-stage sampling procedure was adopted in drawing the sample. Three instruments were used for the study namely the Optimism Scale (OS), Self-Efficacy Scale (SES) and English Language, Mathematics and Biology Achievement Test (ELMBAT). The Research instruments were validated by the two experts in the field of Measurement and Evaluation. To ensure the reliability of the instruments, Cronbach alpha (α) technique was used for all the instruments. The alpha coefficients of 0.75, 0.82 and 0.87 for optimism, self-efficacy and ELMBAT respectively. The data generated were analyzed using simple and multiple regression analysis. Specifically, research question one and two were answered using simple linear regression while research question three was answered using multiple regression. Regarding the hypotheses, hypotheses one and two were tested using t-test associated with simple linear regression while hypotheses three was tested using ANOVA associated with multiple linear regression. Result revealed among others that optimism and self-efficacy significantly independently and jointly relate with academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between optimism and academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Simple regression table showing the relationship between optimism and academic achievement

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate
	.477a	.227	.226	5.76956

Data presentation on the relationship between optimism and academic achievement showed that an R value of 0.477 was gotten with an R² value of 0.227 and an adjusted R² of 0.226. On the basis of the R² value obtained, it can be seen that optimism accounted for 22.7% variation in the academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State. That means optimism has a strong positive relationship with academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between optimism and academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State.

Table 2: Summary of analysis, of regression associated with t-test on the relationship between optimism and academic achievement.

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	11.251	.736		15.288	.000
	Optimism	.527	.039	.477	13.516	.000

The result further showed that the beta of .477 and a t-value of 13.516 was obtained when the obtained regression coefficient was tested for significance, based on the sig-value of 0.000 which is less than the alpha of 0.05. This result therefore indicates that optimism significantly relate with academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Research Question: 2: What is the relationship between self-efficacy and academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State?

Table 3: Summary simple regression of the relationship between self-efficacy and academic achievement

R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Adj Error of the estimate
.136a	.018	.017	6.50284

Table 3 Shows that the joint relationship between self-efficacy yielded an R value of 0.136 this is, alongside a coefficient of determination R² of 0.018 and an adjusted coefficient of determination an (adj R²) of 0.017, it is deduced that 1.8% of the changes in academic achievement are dependent on the changes of the combined effect of self-efficacy. On the other hand, the remaining, 98.2% of the changes in academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State are attributable to factors outside self-efficacy. This showed that self-efficacy has a low positive relationship with academic achievement.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between self-efficacy and academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State.

Table 4: Summary of analysis, of regression associated with t-test on the relationship between self-efficacy and academic achievement.

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	23.897	.974		2525	.000
	Self-efficacy	-.165	.048	-.136	-3.412	.001

The result further showed that the beta of -.136 and a t-value of -3.412 was obtained when the obtained regression coefficient was tested for significance, based on the sig-value of 0.001 which is less than the alpha of 0.05. This result therefore indicates that self-efficacy significantly relate with academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Research Question 3: *To what extent do optimism and self-efficacy jointly relate with academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State?*

Table 5. Summary of multiple regression of the joint relationship between academic achievement by optimism and self-esteem

R	R ²	Adj.R ²	Std error of the estimate
.492a	.242	.234	5.73845

The answer to research question three as shown in Table 5 indicated that a multiple regression coefficient of 0.492 was obtained on optimism and self-esteem as it jointly relate to academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State, with the coefficient of determination, R², of 0.242, and an adjusted R² of 0.23. From the R²-value of 0.242, it therefore suggest that 22% of the variations in academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State can be attributed and explained by optimism and self-esteem.

Hypothesis 3: Optimism and self-esteem do not significantly jointly relate with academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State.

Table 6: Multiple Linear Regression coefficient of optimism and self-esteem as it jointly relate to academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	6467.716	6	1077.953	32.735	.000b
	Residual	2028727	616	32.930		
	Total	26752.443	622			

Furthermore, in testing the corresponding null hypotheses, the result indicated that an F-value of 32.735 was obtained at 6 and 616 degrees of freedom with an associated p-value of 0.000. Since the obtained p-value was less than 0.05, it therefore indicate that optimism and self-esteem jointly do relate to academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

Optimism and Academic achievement

From the analysis of research question one and the corresponding null hypothesis in table 1, it was shown that optimism significantly relate to academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State. This relationship was found to be statistically significant when tested at 0.05 level of significance. This result means that students who scored high in the section of optimism also scored low in academic achievement while those who scored low in optimism also scored high in academic achievement. This result is not surprising to the researcher because someone who lacks optimism doesn't understand their own thoughts and feelings or how other people perceive them. People who lack optimism always have to be the center of attention, be in control, and frequently make negative comments without a filter. Also optimism is an attitude reflecting a belief or hope that the outcome of some specific endeavour, or outcomes in general, will be positive and favourable. This means that any student who is high optimism will perform well in his academics.

This result is similar to that obtained by Pablo (2022) who analysed the relationship among academic self-efficacy, optimism, and academic performance. The results of the study revealed significant correlations among self-efficacy, optimism and academic performance. These results emphasise the importance of academic self-efficacy as a mediating variable between the other two variables as well as its central role in the promotion of adaptive behaviours in the classroom, leading to adequate personal development, helping to prevent early school dropout and contributing to a more satisfactory academic experience.

This study is also similar to the findings of Akhmad (2023) who analysed the relationship between level the optimism, learning achievement and character of students. The findings reveal that the students'

optimism is at an excellent level, whereas their learning achievement is in the moderate range. Furthermore, there is a positive and significant correlation between optimism and academic performance. The results indicate that the $f\text{-count} > f\text{-table}$, and the table probability value is 0.000, which is smaller than the significance level of 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), demonstrating a significant outcome. Thus, it can be inferred that the higher the level of optimism, the better the academic performance. The fact that optimism influences learning achievement provides opportunities to boost students' optimism. Consequently, teachers bear the responsibility of enhancing students' optimism, either directly or indirectly. By fostering and elevating an optimistic mindset in students, it is expected that they will enhance their cognitive processes and academic outcomes, paving the way for success.

Finally, this result is in disagreement with the findings of Moradi (2017) who investigated the relationship between academic optimism and academic achievement in boy's high schools students of districts 6, 9 in Tehran city. Descriptive- correlation method was used. The findings are as follows: There was a significant positive relationship between student's academic optimism and academic achievement in boy's high schools of districts 6, 9 in Tehran city. Among students' academic optimism dimensions (students' academic press, students trust in teachers, students identification with school), students' academic press accounted for the highest degree of variance in academic achievement.

Self-efficacy and Academic achievement

From the analysis of research question two and the corresponding null hypothesis in table 3, it was shown that self-efficacy had a significant relationship between academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State. The relationship is statistically significant at 0.5 level of significance. This result implies that students who scored highly on the section of self-efficacy are prone to score low in their academic achievement. However, the reported relationship indicates that all those who score high in self-efficacy also scored low in academic achievement. The result that self-efficacy relate to academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State is not surprising to the researcher. Because a student with poor self-efficacy skills may lack self-confidence and self-esteem and have trouble handling stress and frustration. Often, this might result in anger or anxiety. In more severe cases, it can even lead to poor performance in school. Also self-efficacy is an individual belief in his or her capacity to execute behaviours necessary to produce specific performance attainment.

This result is similar to that obtained by Gerald (2023) who established the relationship between students' self-efficacy and academic performance at Makerere University. Findings showed that the students' self-efficacy and academic performance mean scores are on the same level (high) and 2nd class upper, respectively. However, there is no significant relationship between students' academic self-efficacy and academic performance given the $\rho > .05$ for all constructs (perceived control, competence, persistence and self-regulated learning). Even though the students have a high level of self-efficacy, it may not influence their academic performance in class. Also, this does not mean that the university should not give importance to developing the students' self-efficacy. Also this findings is in line with that of Mbabazi (2016) who determined the influence of attitude and self-efficacy towards academic performance in Mathematics. The results showed a satisfactory level of students' academic performance. It is either positive or negative in terms of the level of attitude towards the subject of mathematics. As for the self-efficacy of the graduates, it is not high or low. When grouped according to gender, no significant difference was observed in attitude and self-efficacy. It was also found that only attitude towards mathematics significantly influenced academic performance. Students who have a positive attitude toward the subject tend to perform well. Therefore, it is possible to improve performance in mathematics by cultivating a positive attitude towards the subject. It is the responsibility of parents, lecturers and other stakeholders to support the students in this field. Mbabazi's checked research focused on only one subject, while the current study was conducted across the entire College of education and external studies among undergraduate students.

Finally, the findings is in line with the findings of Chanana (2023) who examined the relationship between the self-efficacy and academic performance in Graduation level students. The results of the study showed that there is a significant relationship between self-efficacy and academic performance of the

students. Also, we found that there is no significant relationship between self-efficacy and academic performance among students varied by age of course.

CONCLUSION

The study has shown that optimism and self-esteem have different effect on the academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State. This study to knowledge is that this study has empirically shown that optimism and self-esteem collectively relate to academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State. Furthermore, this study is the first in the researcher's opinion that has considered the psychosocial correlates of academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. School counsellors should play an important role in the academic achievement of students by offering and/or referring them for appropriate techniques that will help boost their optimistic behaviour.
2. Parents and teachers should find out the possible ways of improving the self-efficacy of their children. This will boost their sense of self importance and help to better their performance in school.
3. Parents should instill a sense of greater trust between them and the adolescents in order to improve their social development. This will help to increase the rate of optimism among them which will also help to improve their performance in school.

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